

Towards a Model of Support in the Areas of Services of Educational Assistance and Tutoring in Middle Education in Mexico

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Abstract : Adolescence is a neuralgic stage in the formation of every human being, generally at this stage is when the middle school level is studied. In 2006 in Mexico incorporated "mentoring" space to assist students in their integration and participation in life. In public middle schools, is sometimes difficult to be aware of situations that affect students because of the number of them and traditional records management. With this they lose the opportunity to provide timely support as a preventive way. In order to provide this support, it is required to know the students by detecting the relevant information that has greater impact on their learning process. This research is looking to check if it is possible to identify student's relevant information to detect when it is at risk, and then to propose a model to manage in a proper way such information.

Keywords : adolescence, mentoring, middle school students, mentoring system support

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